

**TEACHERS' TEACHING STYLES, LEARNERS' LEARNING STYLES AND LEVEL
OF READING PERFORMANCE OF LOWER MADAMBA AND UPPER MADAMBA
DISTRICTS LANA DEL
SUR II: S.Y 2021-2022 BASIS FOR
AN ACTION PLAN**

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to identify the teaching styles of teachers, the learning styles of learners, and the effects on learners' reading performance in the Lower Madamba District, Division of Lanao del Sur II, for the school year 2021-2022. It involved 38 English teachers and 82 randomly selected learners from the Lower and Upper Madamba Districts. Using a descriptive correlational research method, the study examined the relationships between variables. Key findings included that the majority of teachers were middle-aged, married, experienced (16-18 years), and earned between 21k-30k per month. Most learners were 13 years old, female, and from families earning P5,000 to P9,000 monthly, with parents generally having elementary education. Teachers moderately agreed on using various teaching styles (expert, formal authority, personal model, facilitator, delegator) but strongly agreed on using personal model, delegator, and formal authority styles. Learners performed better with auditory teaching methods. Many students in Grades III, IV, V, and VI were at the frustration level in reading, needing assistance. There were significant differences in teaching styles based on teacher profiles and significant relationships between teaching styles, learning styles, and learners' reading performance. An action plan is proposed based on these findings.

Keywords. *Teachers' teaching style, Learners' Learning styles, PHIL-IRI, Reading performance, Action plan*

INTRODUCTION

Stakeholders worldwide strive for quality education, which prepares learners to meet life's challenges and achieve their dreams. Quality education relies on qualified and effective teachers who employ appropriate teaching styles. According to the Grasha-Riechmann teaching style survey, there are five teaching styles: Expert, Formal Authority, Personal Model, Facilitator, and Delegator. Effective teachers use styles that align with diverse student learning styles, which are visual, auditory, and kinesthetic.

Teachers must be knowledgeable and competent to address the diversity of learners. The term "learning styles" refers to the preferential ways students absorb, process, comprehend, and retain information. An individual's learning style can significantly impact their educational experience. Effective education requires the application of knowledge, skills, and attributes to meet the needs of both individuals and society. Teaching theories generally fall into teacher-centered or student-centered approaches. Traditional styles (Expert, Formal Authority, Personal Model) are often effective in rural areas with limited technology, while progressive styles (Facilitator, Delegator) are more suitable in urban areas with advanced technology.

Reading is a critical skill that underpins lifelong learning and social and economic advancement. Effective teaching styles can enhance students' reading skills, which are crucial for their overall learning success. The PHIL-IRI assessment tool evaluates the reading proficiency of elementary pupils, identifying their levels as independent, instructional, or frustration. This information helps educators plan targeted reading instructions and propose action plans to improve reading proficiency.

The researcher, an Assistant Professor IV and former TIC/Principal at Linuk Elementary School, has observed a mismatch between teaching styles, learning styles, and reading performance. The declining reading skills of pupils in the Lower and Upper Madamba Districts, as evidenced by low PHIL-IRI scores, indicate a need for assessment and improvement. This study aims to address the low reading scores by proposing an action plan to enhance the reading performance of learners in these districts.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive correlational research method to identify the relationship between teachers' teaching styles and learners' learning styles on the reading performance of students in the Lower Madamba and Upper Madamba Districts. The correlational method was used to examine relationships between variables, while descriptive research described the population and characteristics of the study subjects.

The study profiled teachers based on age, civil status, training/seminar hours, length of teaching experience in English, highest educational attainment, and monthly

income. Students' profiles included age, gender, parents' occupations, family monthly income, parents' educational attainment, and reading performance. A standardized questionnaire was adapted for the study, and data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Madamba, Lanao Del Sur, covering Lower Madamba District and Upper Madamba District, both known for their beautiful sceneries, mountains, hills, rivers, and forests. Madamba, one of the 32 municipalities of Lanao Del Sur, is bounded by a mountain to the north, the twin peaks of Baya mountain and Lake Dapao to the south, Mount Matongan to the northwest, and a river to the east. The Madamba National High School is located eastward of the central Biyalbalan hills. The districts include several schools, each with distinct characteristics and challenges:

Madamba Central Elementary School teaches pupils from Kindergarten to Grade VI, with 445 students in 10 instructional rooms, but lacks reliable power. Toka Elementary School serves 352 students from Kindergarten to Grade VI, with 8 instructional rooms and no reliable power. Lumbaca-Ingud Elementary School, serving Grades I to VI, has 201 students and 5 instructional rooms powered by a grid. Cabasaran Elementary School, with 236 students in Grades I to VI, has only 2 instructional rooms and no reliable power. Liangan Primary School teaches 110 students in Grades I to IV, with no instructional rooms or reliable power.

Moriatao Gadong Elementary School serves 337 students from Grades I to VI, with 6 instructional rooms and no reliable power. Palao Primary School, with 345 students in Grades I to VI, has 6 instructional rooms and no reliable power. Pantar Primary School teaches 246 students in Grades I to IV, with no instructional rooms or reliable power. Punud Primary School, with 272 students in Grades I to IV, has 3 instructional rooms and no reliable power. Tabaran Primary School serves 135 students in Grades I to IV, with no instructional rooms or reliable power.

Tambo Elementary School, with 372 students from Grades I to VI, has 3 instructional rooms and no reliable power. Uyaan Central Elementary School teaches 557 students in Grades I to VI, with 6 instructional rooms and no reliable power. Finally, Linuk Elementary School serves 265 students from Kindergarten to Grade VI, with 7 instructional rooms and no reliable power, and the researcher of this study is the designated School Principal.

Research Participants

The researcher employed two groups of respondents to answer the questionnaire. The first group of respondents were the teachers, the researcher employed total population sampling in gathering data. They were represented by thirty-eight (38) teachers handling English subject from Grade III to Grade VI with the exclusion of those teachers handling ancillary services like Planning Officers, Guidance Counsellors,

Librarians and Disbursing Officers. The other groups of respondents were eighty-two (82) learners from Grade III to Grade VI levels. The researcher employed systematic random sampling for the learners' respondent.

Research Instrument

In the study, Part I, Section I (Teachers) utilized a questionnaire format based on Romerick's (2015) framework to gather personal information and details on teaching experience from the teachers involved. This section aimed to establish a comprehensive profile of the educators participating in the research.

Part I, Section II (Teachers) focused on evaluating the effectiveness of teaching styles using a Rating Scale adapted from Grasha-Riechmann (1996), as referenced by Gill (2013). This section included 40 questions designed to assess various dimensions of teaching styles and their perceived impact on classroom dynamics and learning outcomes.

Part II, Section I (Learners) employed a questionnaire format based on Stenberg & Wagner (1992), cited by Mangandingan (2017), to gather demographic data and details on family background from the learner participants. This section aimed to provide contextual information about the students involved in the study.

Part II, Section II (Learners) utilized a Likert Scale adapted from Dods Dodong & Diane Scaiff (2005), as referenced by Mangandingan (2017). This section consisted of 20 items designed to assess the learning styles of the learners, focusing on how they perceive and engage with different approaches to learning.

Overall, these instruments were strategically chosen to gather comprehensive data on both teachers' practices and learners' experiences, providing insights into educational dynamics within the study context.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher initially obtained formal approval from the Dean of the Graduate School of IMCC to conduct a study involving English teachers and selected pupils from Lower Madamba and Upper Madamba Districts. Upon receiving written permission from relevant authorities, the researcher personally distributed questionnaires in each school with assistance from teachers. Respondents were informed that questionnaires would be collected after five days, after which the researcher retrieved them. Subsequently, data collected from the questionnaires were categorized and subjected to descriptive analysis. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS with the assistance of a statistician, and the findings were interpreted by the researcher. This process ensured systematic data collection and rigorous analysis to derive meaningful insights from the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Age of the Teacher Respondents.

AGE	Frequency	Percent
26-30	7	18.40
31-35	4	10.50
36-40	1	2.60
41-45	2	5.30
46-50	12	31.60
51 ABOVE	12	31.60
Total	38	100

Part I discusses the profile of the teachers in terms of age, civil status, length of teaching experience in English subject, highest educational attainment and monthly income.

Table 1 shows that there was an equal number (12 or 31.6%) of respondents who belonged to the 46-50 and 51 above age brackets, 7 or 18.4% belonged to the 26-30 age bracket and 4 or 10.5% of the teacher respondents were 31-35 years old. This means that majority of the teacher respondents were at least 46 years old. This implies that they were more matured, they were experienced as a teacher. It is easy for them to vary their teaching styles.

Table 2: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Civil Status of the Teacher Respondents.

CIVIL STATUS	Frequency	Percent
Married	34	89.50
Single	1	2.60
Widow	3	7.90
Total	38	100

As could be gleaned in Table 2, there were 34 or 89.5% of the teacher respondents were married, 3 or 7.9% were widowed and 1 or 2.6% was single. This means that majority of the respondents have families. Hence, they can adopt a teaching styles that is more useful to their children at school just like a teaching styles which is useful to their real children at home.

Table 3: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Length of Teaching Experience in English Subject of the Teacher Respondent.

Length of Teaching Experience in English Subject	Frequency	Percent
1-6 years	3	7.90
7-15 years	7	18.50
16-18 years	11	28.90
19-21years	3	7.90
22-24 years	3	7.90
25 above	11	28.90
Total	38	100

It could be observed in Table 3 that there were equally 11 or 28.9% who had been teaching English for 16-18 years and at least 25 years, 7 or 18.4% who had been in the field for 7-15 years and 3 or 7.9% for 1-6, 19-21 and 22-24 brackets. This implies that majority of the teacher respondents were experienced in terms of teaching English.

Table 4: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Highest Educational Attainment of the Teacher Respondents.

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Master of Arts	3	7.90
BSE-MA	2	5.30
BSEED	30	78.90
ETC	2	5.30
Others	1	2.60
Total	38	100

As could be observed in Table 4, there were 30 or 78.9% of the teacher respondents graduated BSEED, 3 or 7.9% earned their Master of Arts degree and 2 or 5.3% had earned units in Masteral and etc. This implies that majority of the respondents were BSEED graduates. Hence, they are qualified and knowledgeable enough to adopt learning styles that can cater diversity of learners.

Table 5: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Monthly Income of the Teacher Respondents.

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percent
Above P31,000.00	4	10.50
P21,000.00-P30,000.00	20	52.60
P19,000.00-P20,000.00	14	36.80
Total	38	100

Table 5 shows that there were 20 or 52.6% of the teacher respondents was earning P21k-P30k a month, 14 or 6.8% was receiving a monthly salary of P19k-P20k and 4 or 10.5% had been earning at least P31,000 a month. This means that the teacher respondents were given remuneration which sufficed to their hard work.

Table 6: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Age of the Learner Respondents.

AGE	Frequency	Percent
10	1	1.20
11	2	2.40
12	20	24.40
13	38	46.30
14	17	20.70
15	4	4.90
Total	82	100

Part II discusses the profile of the learners in terms of age, gender, parents' occupation, family's monthly income and parents' educational attainment.

As could be observed in Table 6, there were 38 or 46.3% of the learner respondents was 13 years old, 20 or 24.4% was 12 and 17 or 20.7% was 14 years old. This means that majority of the learners had been normally admitted to their corresponding grade level.

Table 7: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Gender of the Learner Respondents.

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	32	39
Female	50	61
Total	82	100

Table 7 shows that there were 50 or 61% of the learner respondents were female and 32 or 39% was male. This means that there were more female students who were admitted to school than male ones.

Table 8: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Father's Occupation of the Learner Respondents.

Father Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Gov't Employee	1	1.2
Non-Govt	11	13.4
Self Employed	32	39
Fisherman	1	1.2
No work	23	28
Farmer	1	1.2
Tailor	6	7.3
Carpenter	1	1.2
OFW	4	4.9
Business	2	2.4
Total	82	100

It could be observed in Table 8 that there were 32 or 39% of the fathers of the learner respondents was self-employed, 23 or 28% of their fathers had no jobs and 11 or 13.4% was non-government employees. This means that majority of the fathers of the learners were managing their own businesses.

Table 9: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Mother's Occupation of the Learner Respondents

Mothers Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Gov't Employee	2	2.40
Non-Govt	11	13.40
Self Employed	34	41.50
Housewife	7	8.50
Farmer	22	26.80
Dressmaking	3	3.60
OFW	2	2.40
Business	1	1.20
Total	82	100

Table 9 shows that there were 34 or 41.5% of the mothers of the learners were self-employed, 22 or 26.8% of their mothers were farmers and 11 or 13.4% were

employed in a private sector. This means that majority of the learners came from families who run their own businesses.

Table 10: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Family's Monthly Income of the Learner Respondents

Family's Monthly Income	Frequency	Percent
Above P20,000.00	2	2.40
P15,000.00-P19,000.00	3	3.70
P10,000.00-P14,000.00	11	13.40
P9,000.00-P5,000.00	65	79.30
below P5,000.00	1	1.20
Total	82	100

Table 10 shows that there were 65 or 79.3% of the respondents came from a family who was earning P5,000 to P9,000 per month, 11 or 13.4% of the learner respondents came from a home which was earning P10,000 to P14,000 monthly and 3 or 3.7% were raised by parents who had a combined monthly income of P15,000 to P19,000.

Table 11: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Fathers' Educational Attainment of the Learner Respondents.

Father's Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
BS degree w/master	4	4.90
BS degree	2	2.40
HS Graduate	24	29.30
Elem Grad.	51	62.20
others: Gr. 2	1	1.20
Total	82	100

As could be gleaned in Table 11, there were 51 or 62.2% of the fathers of the learner respondents were elementary graduates, 24 or 29.3% of their fathers had finished their secondary level and 4 or 4.9% had earned masteral units. This means that majority of the fathers of the learner respondents were not able to finish their studies, they were elementary graduates only.

Table 12: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Mothers' Educational Attainment of the Learner Respondents.

Mother's Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Master's degree	4	4.9

BS degree w/master	3	3.7
BS degree	21	25.6
HS Graduate	53	64.6
Elem Grad.	1	1.2
Total	82	100

As could be gleaned in Table 12, there were 53 or 64.6% of the mothers of the learner respondents were high school graduates, 21 or 25.6% of their mothers earned their bachelor's degree and 4 or 4.9% of their mothers were able to earn degree in masters. This means that the mothers of the respondents were more inclined to studying than their fathers as presented in Table 11.

Table 13: Mean Distribution of the Identified Teaching Styles of the Teacher Respondents.

1-EXPERT	Mean	Description
1. Facts, concepts, and principles are the most important things that students should acquire.	4.08	Moderately Agree
2. Sharing my knowledge and expertise with students is very important to me.	4.05	Moderately Agree
3. What I have to say about a topic is important for students to acquire a broader perspective on the issues in that area.	4.79	Strongly Agree
4. I want students to leave this course well prepared for further work in this area.	2.42	Moderately Disagree
5. Lecturing is a significant part of how I teach each of the class sessions.	2.53	Moderately Disagree
6. My expertise is typically used to resolve disagreements about content issues.	2.55	Moderately Disagree
7. Students might describe me as a "storehouse of knowledge" who dispenses the fact, principles, and concepts they need.	3.21	Undecided
8. There is more material in this course than I have time available to cover it.	3.13	Undecided
Weighted Mean	3.35	Undecided
2-FORMAL AUTHORITY		
1. I set high standards for students in this class.	4.82	Strongly Agree
2. I give students negative feedback when their performance is unsatisfactory.	4.82	Strongly Agree

3. Students would describe my standards and expectations as somewhat strict and rigid	4.84	Strongly Agree
4. It is my responsibility to define what students must learn and how they should learn it.	4.00	Moderately Agree
5. Students receive frequent verbal and/or written comments on their performance.	4.13	Moderately Agree
6. This course has very specific goals and objectives that I want to accomplish.	3.00	Undecided
7. My expectations for what I want students to do in this class are clearly defined in the syllabus.	4.71	Strongly Agree
8. Students might describe me as a "coach" who works closely with someone to correct problems in how they think and behave.	4.97	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	4.41	Strongly Agree
3- PERSONAL MODEL		
1. What I say and do models appropriate ways for students to think about issues in the content.	4.26	Strongly Agree
2. I spend time consulting with students on how to improve their work on individual and/or group projects.	4.16	Moderately Agree
3. I typically show students how and what to do in order to master course content.	4.89	Strongly Agree
4. Examples from my personal experiences often are used to illustrate points about the material.	4.89	Strongly Agree
5. I often show students how they can use various principles and concepts.	4.45	Strongly Agree
6. I provide very clear guidelines for how I want tasks completed in this course.	4.95	Strongly Agree
7. Eventually, many students begin to think like me about course content.	4.95	Strongly Agree
8. My standards and expectations help students develop the discipline they need to learn.	4.97	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	4.69	Strongly Agree
4- FACILITATOR		
1. My teaching goals and methods address a variety of student learning styles.	2.50	Moderately Disagree

2. Activities in this class encourage students to develop their own ideas about content issues.	4.76	Strongly Agree
3. Small group discussions are employed to help students develop their ability to think critically.	2.32	Moderately Disagree
4. I guide students' work on course projects by asking questions, exploring options, and suggesting alternative ways to do things.	2.68	Undecided
5. Course activities encourage students to take initiative and responsibility for their learning.	2.11	Moderately Disagree
6. I solicit student advice about how and what to teach in this course.	4.05	Moderately Agree
7. Students can make choices among activities in order to complete course requirements.	4.08	Moderately Agree
8. I give students a lot of personal support and encouragement to do well in this course.	4.18	Moderately Agree
Weighted Mean	3.34	Undecided
5-DELEGATOR		
1. Students typically work on course projects alone with little supervision from me.	2.76	Undecided
2. Activities in this class encourage students to develop their own ideas about content issues.	4.68	Strongly Agree
3. Students design one of more self-directed learning experiences.	4.55	Strongly Agree
4. Developing the ability of students to think and work independently is an important goal.	4.84	Strongly Agree
5. Students take responsibility for teaching part of the class sessions.	4.74	Strongly Agree
6. Students set their own pace for completing independent and/or group projects.	4.89	Strongly Agree
7. My approach to teaching is similar to a manager of a work group who delegates tasks and responsibilities to subordinates.	4.92	Strongly Agree
8. I assume the role of a resource person who is available to students whenever they need help.	3.98	Moderately Agree
Weighted Mean	4.42	Strongly Agree

Part III discusses the identified teaching styles of teachers namely expert, formal authority, personal model, facilitator and delegator teaching styles.

As presented in Table 13, the teacher respondents had strongly agreed that they were practicing the personal model teaching style with a weighted mean of 4.69. Teacher respondents had strongly agreed that they had established clear goals, standards and expectations that inculcated discipline among their students ($m=4.97$). Also, the teacher respondents strongly agreed on setting guidelines with how their task should be completed and in turn, the students had fully internalized how their teachers managed them to the extent that they could actually think how the teachers think ($m=4.95$). Furthermore, the teacher respondents strongly agreed on demonstrating how and what to do their desired activities for the class, illustrating their own life experience to help students visualize the material ($m=4.89$).

Table 13 shows that the teacher respondents strongly agreed that they had been utilizing the delegator teaching style with a weighted mean of 4.42. The teacher respondents strongly agreed to act as managers to their subordinates, which in the classroom set-up were the students, assigning and delegating them their respective tasks and responsibilities ($m=4.92$). In time, students were able to come up with their own pacing in accomplishing tasks given to them be it individual or group project ($m=4.89$). Generally, the teacher respondents strongly agreed that the main goal of instruction is to effect change in the behaviors of the students, honing and nurturing them into becoming individuals who could think and work without depending on others ($m=4.84$).

Table 13 further shows that the teacher respondents strongly agreed that they were using the formal authority teaching style with a weighted mean of 4.41. The teacher respondents strongly agreed that their students had perceived the teachers as coaches who were hand-on to the students, making necessary corrections if the need arises ($m=4.97$) and that students thought of the teachers as somewhat strict and rigid in terms of standards and what was expected of them ($m=4.84$). Generally, the teacher respondents strongly agreed that they had set standards and expectations for their students, providing feedback to unsatisfactory students' performance ($m=4.82$).

Anthony F. Grasha and Sheryl Riechmann-Hruska (1996) as cited by Gill (2013) there are five primary teaching styles that describe the prevalent approaches in the classroom. teaching styles are as follows: Expert- possesses knowledge and expertise that students need. Strives to maintain status as an expert by displaying detailed knowledge and challenging students to enhance their competence. Concerned with transmitting information and ensuring that students are well prepared. Formal Authority- possesses status among student because of knowledge and role as a faculty. Concerned with providing positive/negative feedback, establishing learning goals, expectations, and rules of conduct. Concerned with "correct, acceptable, and standard ways to do things". Personal model- believes in "teaching by example", establishes a prototype for how to think and behave. Oversees and directs by showing how to do things and encouraging students to observe and then emulate the instructor's approach. Facilitator- emphasizes

the personal nature of teacher-student interactions. Guides students by asking questions, exploring options, suggesting alternatives, and encouraging informed decisions. Develop student capacity for independent responsibility. Works as consultant on student projects and provides support and encouragement. And Delegator- concerned with developing students' capacity to function autonomously. Students work independently on projects or as a part of autonomous teams. The teacher is available at the request of students as a resource. Anthony F. Grasha and Sheryl Riechmann-Hruska (1996) as cited by Gill (2013).

The Grasha-Riechmann (1996) as cited by Ford, J.H., Robinson, J.M. & Wise, M.E.(2016) model integrates individual teaching and learning style and demonstrates how the stylistic qualities of teachers and students can enhance the nature and quality of the learning experience While most teachers have a preferred teaching style, they use a mix of styles to engage a wide array of learners who might prefer interactive, experiential or didactic teaching approaches.

Table 14: Mean Distribution of the Summary Identified Teaching Styles of the Teachers' Respondents

Teaching Styles	Mean	Description
1-EXPERT	3.35	Undecided
2-FORMAL AUTHORITY	4.41	Strongly Agree
3- PERSONAL MODEL	4.69	Strongly Agree
4- FACILITATOR	3.34	Undecided
5-DELEGATOR	4.42	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	4.04	Moderately Agree

Table 14 shows that the teacher respondents moderately agreed on the identified teaching styles with a weighted mean of 4.04. On the other hand, they strongly agreed that they were utilizing the personal model (m=4.69), delegator (m=4.42) and formal authority (m=4.41) teaching styles.

According to Borich (1997) as cited by Rudhumbu (2014) teaching serves as a guide and provides direction in every classroom conducted by the teacher. Teachers being a focal person of education must be competent and knowledgeable in order to guide the learners to the right path. Borich (1997) as cited by Rudhumbu, (2014) again pointed out that the teacher is considered as the most important variable in the learners' environment. He lays a crucial role in initiating and maintaining student's motivation in classroom by selectively adopting effective strategies in facilitating and enhancing learning in accordance with student's motivation.

Tuan (2011) conducted a study to identify how teachers understand their students learning preferences as well as the extent of mismatch between

students' and teachers' styles which has led to students' low performance and frustration.

Effective teaching requires flexibility, creativity and responsibility in order to provide an instructional environment able to respond to the learner's individual needs. As Tomlinson (2015) puts it, beyond the experiential evidence that pervasive uniformity in teaching fails many learners, there is a reason in both theory and research to support a movement towards an instruction attentive to students' variance manifested in at least three areas: the student's readiness, interest, and learning profile. One of the ongoing challenges the university are facing is related to matching the teaching strategies with the students' learning styles in order to improve the academic achievement. Tomlinson (2015).

A teacher's teaching style (authoritative, authoritarian and permissive) affects students' experience in school. It can provoke functional or non-functional perceptions of learning, self-efficacy and schoolwork, thus an appropriate teaching style can help prevent early school leaving (Leban, 2015).

Table 15: Mean Distribution of the Identified Learning Styles of the Learner Respondents.

Auditory	Mean	Description
I understand my teacher better when he/she tells me instruction.	4.93	Always
I learn better when someone tells me how to do something in class.	4.67	Always
I remember things I have heard in class better than things I have read.	4.88	Always
I learn better in class when the teacher gives a lecture.	4.89	Always
I learn better in class when I listen to someone.	4.39	Always
I study while doing bodily movement such as holding my hears or moving my feet/hands.	4.44	Always
I learn better when I do things in the class.	4.71	Always
Weighted Mean	4.70	Always
Kinesthetic		
I enjoyed learning in the class by doing experiments.	4.54	Always
I understand things better in class when I participate in role-playing.	4.40	Always
I learn better in class when I can participate in the activities.	4.57	Always
Weighted Mean	4.50	Always
Visual		

I learn better by reading what the teacher writes on board.	4.62	Always
I remember better when I read instructions.	4.51	Always
I understand better when I read instructions.	4.73	Always
I learn better by reading than by listening to someone.	4.45	Always
I learn more by reading textbooks than by listening to lectures.	4.46	Always
I learn more when I conduct experiment of the lesson.	4.70	Always
I learn more when I make something for a class project.	4.62	Always
I learn better when I makes drawings as I study.	4.54	Always
I remember better what I have learned when I physically holds it.	4.67	Always
I enjoy making something for a class project.	4.76	Always
Weighted Mean	4.61	Always

Part IV discusses the identified learning styles of the learner namely auditory, kinesthetic and visual learning styles.

Data on Table 15 shows that the learners had always applied the auditory learning style with a weighted mean of 4.70. Learner respondents had always understood their teachers when their teachers tell them what to do (m=4.93) and they learn better in class when their teachers utilize the traditional lecture method (m=4.89) and they can easily remember things which they heard than read (m=4.88).

Table 15 shows that the students always applied the visual learning style with a weighted mean of 4.61. Students had always enjoyed when they do class projects (m=4.76), understood lessons better when they were reading the instructions and conducting experiments (m=4.70).

Table 15 further shows that the learners had always applied the kinesthetic learning style with a weighted mean of 4.50. Students learn better when they were performing activities (m=4.57) and doing some experiments (m=4.54) and participating in role-plays (m=4.40). This means that the students were better when they were the one doing things rather than just hearing and seeing.

Learning is defined as a process that brings behavioral changes to a person. It is a skill that must be acquired by individuals in their studies and later, in their careers. Landry, et al. (2013).

Table 16: Mean Distribution of the Summary Identified Learning Styles of the Learner Respondents.

Learning Styles	Mean	Description
Auditory	4.70	Always
Kinesthetic	4.50	Always
Visual	4.61	Always
Weighted Mean	4.60	Always

Table 16 shows that the students had always applied the identified learning styles with a weighted mean of 4.60. Specifically, students perform better when they employ auditory (m=4.70), visual (m=4.61) and kinesthetic (m=4.50) learning styles.

Students tend to perceive information differently, such as by “viewing and listening, reflection and action, to reasoning logically and intuitively and also scrutinizing and visualizing” (Felder and Henriques, 1995) as cited by (Wan Shaaidi, 2014).

Table 17: Frequency Distribution of the level of reading performance of learners based on PHIL-IRI results

Reading Performance	Phil-IRI Score:	Pre-test f	%	Post-test f	%
Independent	90-100	27	32.9%	24	29.3%
Instructional Frustration	75-89-74 and below	24 30	29.3% 36.6%	28 30	34.1% 36.6%
Non-reader	00	1	1.2%	0	00
TOTAL		82	100%	82	100%

Part V. The Level of Reading Performance of Learners Based on PHIL-IRI Results

Table 17 shows that out of 82 respondents 20 pupils from Grades III, IV, V, and VI belongs to Frustration level on their Pre-test and Post-test. 13 pupils belong to the Instructional level on their Pre-test but it decreases to 13 on the post-test. 6 pupils belong to Independent level on the pre-test but it decreases to 5 pupils on the post test. For non-reader, there was a non-reader in the pre-test only. This implies that the number pupils increase before and after the test in each level of reading performance using PHIL-IRI.

The key to learning is better reading skills. But this reading skill need not be confined to English only. The ability to read and write in any language or dialect is what is important, because the ability to read is highly valued and important for social and economic advancement. From this life-long learning or survival skill, one can develop the

ability to learn for life. MC Ginnis and Smith (1962) as cited by Romerick (2015) pointed out that reading is a multifaceted process involving word recognition, comprehension, fluency and motivation to understand its importance, one must integrate these facets. It is advisable to keep on reading because reading improve our knowledge acquisition and at the same time it will help us to decipher new words and phrases that they come across in everyday conversations.

Reading is fundamentally important for success. The reality is there is no one reading program that is the best. Children learn to read in different ways and differ in the style of instruction they need to become proficient readers. It is evident that there are many reading programs available to teach children to read. It is also evident that there is not “one” best program to use because individuals integrate information differently using each method.

In the research of Olivar (2014) emphasized reading is a habit where students learn, gain knowledge and develop new skills. In order to develop an effective design to educate public school pupils with reading skills, assessment is done to find out the status of their reading proficiency. One of the assessment tool used is called Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI).

Flojo (2007) as cited by Romerick (2015) emphasized that based on Phil-IRI, determined the strength and weaknesses of students. Her study was done to analyze the learners’ difficulties in reading and defining the source of their difficulties in reading comprehension. Her study revealed that learners should be guided to be more aware of their level of achievement as well as specific strengths and weaknesses in reading. With increased learners’ awareness, the instruction becomes more effective.

In the research of Flores (2019) emphasized that action research develops the learners in terms of their reading comprehension skills. In this connection, the researcher-initiated enhancement for the remedial reading program through the interactive instructional strategy to improve reading comprehension among the learners.

Table 18: Significant Difference in the Teachers’ Teaching Styles when grouped according to their Profile

		t	p-value	Significanc e	Decision
Teacher s Profile vs. Teachin g Styles	AGE	16.40 1	0.000	Significant	Reject
	CIVIL STATUS	9.168	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Length of Teaching	15.01 5	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Educational Attainment	18.99	0.000	Significant	Reject

Monthly Income	21.64	0.000	Significant	Reject
	7			

Part VI discusses the significant difference in the teachers' teaching style when they were grouped according to their profile. Since the obtained p-values in Table 18 were less than the level of significance then, there is a significant difference in the teachers' teaching styles when grouped according to their profile. This means that teachers of different profile would have employed a teaching style different from others.

Table 19: Significant Difference in the Learners' Learning Styles when grouped according to their Profile.

		t	p-value	Significance	Decision
Learners Profile vs. Learning Styles	AGE	38.740	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Gender	29.700	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Father Occupation	18.115	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Mothers Occupation	18.409	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Family's Monthly Income	45.571	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Father's Educational Attainment	74.861	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Mother's Educational Attainment	73.600	0.000	Significant	Reject

Part VII discusses the significant difference in the learners' learning styles when grouped according to their profile.

Since the obtained p-values in Table 19 were less than the level of significance then, there is a significant difference in the learning styles of the learners. This means that learners who came from families different from others would employ a learning style that could also be different from them.

Table 20: The Significant Relationship between the Teachers' Teaching Styles and Learners' Level of Reading Performance.

	R	p-value	Significance	Decision
Teachers Teaching Styles vs. Learners Level of Reading Performance	0.52575	0.000	Significant	Reject

Table 20 shows the relationship between the teachers teaching styles and the learners level of reading performance. The p-value of both two variables were less than .05 level of significance. (p-value =0.000). Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers teaching styles and the learners level of reading performance. This would mean that the increase in the value of the teachers teaching style the value of the learners' level of reading performance will also increase. This implies that if the teachers teaching styles will improve, the learners level of reading performance will also improve.

Table 21: The Significant Relationship between Learners' Learning Styles and Their Learners' level of Reading Performance

	r	p-value	Significance	Decision
Learners Learning Styles vs. Learners Level of Reading Performance	0.604	0.000	Significant	Reject

Part IX. The Significant Relationship between Learners Learning Styles and Learners' Level of Reading Performance.

Table 21 reflected the relationship between the learners learning styles and the learners level of reading performance.

In a study, Naimie et al (2010) investigated the influence of matching or mismatching learning and teaching styles on the achievement of learners. The authors

concluded that the students showed a positive attitude and higher attainment when their teachers accommodated their needs and preferences.

The table shows that the p-value of the two variables, learners learning styles and the learners level of reading performance is less than 0.05 level of significance (p-value= 0.000). This means that there is significant relationship between learners learning styles and the learners level of reading performance. This implies that as the learners learning styles improved and the learners level of reading performance will also improve.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings of the study, the following were the conclusions drawn;

There was an equal number of respondents who belonged to the 46-50 and 51 above age brackets, majority were married, who had been teaching English for 16-18 years, and graduated BEED. Majority of the teachers' respondents was earning 21k-30k a month.

Most of the learner respondents in this study were 13 years old, majority were female whose fathers and mothers were self-employed. Majority of the respondents came from a family who was earning P5,000 to P9,000 per month. Majority of the father and mothers were elementary graduates.

With regards to the teaching styles of teachers namely expert, formal authority, personal model, facilitator and delegator teaching styles, it was found out that the teacher respondents moderately agreed on the identified teaching styles. On the other hand, they strongly agreed that they were utilizing the personal model, delegator and formal authority, teaching styles.

As to the pupils identified learning styles, the pupils perform better when the teachers employ auditory. Out of the total respondents who took the PHIL-IRI test, more pupils from Grades III, IV, V, and VI belongs to Frustration level on their Pre-test and Post-test. This means that the pupils can read with assistance coming from the teachers

There is a significant difference in the teachers' teaching styles when grouped according to their profile. There is a significant difference in the learning styles of the learners. There is significant relationship between the teachers teaching styles and the learners level of reading performance. There is significant relationship between learners learning styles and the learners level of reading performance.

Recommendations

- As a result of the study, the following recommendations were proposed;
- 1.The teacher must be and Expert teacher by;
 - a.Possessing knowledge and expertise that learners need;

- b. Striving to maintain status as an expert by displaying detailed knowledge and challenging learners to enhance their competence; and
 - c. Have the concern with transmitting information and ensuring that students are well prepared.
2. Teachers must be a good facilitator, they must;
- a. emphasize the personal nature of teacher-learner interactions;
 - b. guide pupils by asking questions, exploring options, suggesting alternatives, and encouraging informed decisions;
 - c. develop pupils' capacity for independent responsibility; and
 - d. work as consultant on pupils' projects and provides support and encouragement.
3. Develop pupils reading skills and reading with comprehensions by means of;
- a. Utilizing all readings materials available and encourage the learners to read, starting from easiest materials;
 - b. Relating reading to other areas of the pupil's life;
 - c. Creating activities that would increase pupils' vocabulary through fun and games; and
 - d. Creating a bulletin that would trace pupils progress in reading and putting encouraging remarks therein.

Furthermore, it has been proven that learners' learning style and teachers' teaching style in teaching affect the reading performance. Therefore, teachers should employ teaching style based on the learning style of the learner to improve his reading performance. In the study at hand, majority of the learners preferred Auditory Learning Style. So the teachers must take into consideration that He /She must use teaching style that is most favorable to his learning style. They must learn to discover and consider the learning styles of the learners and emerge to the different teachers' teaching styles.

Teachers should be effective and efficient during teaching and learning process. They should monitor the reading performance of their learners from time to time whether or not it is improving. Conduct remedial class if needed and review class if most of them got low score. And that monitoring will be conducted before, during and after the class proper. They are required to attain trainings, workshops, seminars and other capability building on learning and teaching styles. Academic heads should send their in-service teachers to professional lectures and conferences.

A proposed action plan by the School Head of every school answering the following questions: What is the best remedy in order for the learners to improve their level performance in school most specially in reading and comprehension. How to convince and motivate learners to stay in school. Because drop outs and frequent absenteeism is the root cause of the problem we are facing right now.

They cannot read effectively because they are not attending their class. The researcher think that Feeding Program is one of the best action plan to be implemented so that children will stay at school. So the learning process is healthy, sometimes children cannot easily understand, comprehend and grasp information because they are hungry, they cannot think properly if their stomach is empty. Another one is the PTCA meeting

should be mandatory to all the members especially the parents in order for them to assess their children and evaluate their performance.

It is also suggested that the learners should enhance their multiple intelligences. Work on your self-development by adopting multiple learning styles Being active in the class, participate and ask questions to boost their confidence. Read read and read! Read until you can and never give up that will make you better reader.

Hierarchy of position is very much important to solve the root cause of the problem. The Teacher should supervise the child; The Principal should manage the school and supervise the activities of the teacher; The Supervisor should supervise the activities of the principal; and Superintendent – Supervisor; Regional Secretary- Superintendent and so on.

Parental support and involvement is very much needed for your growing children and it will help to improve the children performance of your child because they are inspired motivated and challenged. Moral support is very important. Showing of your tender love and care to their children brings their child to a better future.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research study rigorously followed ethical guidelines to ensure the voluntary involvement of all participants. Every respondent had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any stage if they felt uneasy, and comprehensive measures were implemented to mitigate any potential risks, including physical, social, and psychological harm. The well-being and dignity of elementary teachers who took part in the study were a paramount concern and were diligently protected throughout the research process. Strict protocols were observed to maintain the confidentiality of all research data, safeguarding the rights of respondents and maintaining the credibility and integrity of the scientific and academic aspects of the study. Additionally, stringent practices were adhered to in communicating the study's findings to prevent any instances of plagiarism or research misconduct, ensuring that all dissemination of results upheld the highest standards of academic honesty and transparency.

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